

Physico-Chemical Investigations of some Bivalent Ion Complexes with Oximidobenzotetronic Acid and their Comparison with the Corresponding 2-Nitroso-1-Naphthol Complexes

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The complexes of oximidobenzotetronic acid (OBTA) with iron(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II), zinc(II), cadmium(II) and uranium(VI) ions have been studied conductometrically as well as by *pH*-metric titrations. These metals form 1 : 2 metal : OBTA complexes with the exception of iron (II) and cobalt complexes which have 1 : 3 composition. The logarithm of the stepwise stability constants in 50% aqueous dioxan medium at 21° in presence of 0.3*M* sodium perchlorate being 0.0, 0.0, and 12.70 for iron(II); 4.34 and 4.47 for nickel(II); 0.0 and 7.73 for copper(II) 3.93 and 3.11 for zinc(II); 2.16 and 2.68 for cadmium(II) and 3.48 and 2.90 for uranium(VI) complexes of OBTA. The stability constants of these complexes have been compared with those of 2-nitroso-1-naphthol complexes.

Oximidobenzotetronic acid (OBTA) (I) or 3-nitroso-4-hydroxycoumarin has already been used as an analytical reagent for the gravimetric as well as the spectrophotometric determination of a large number of metal ions¹⁻⁶. The nature of some bivalent metal ion complexes with this reagent has already been reported using spectrophotometric methods⁷. The present communication deals with the conductometric and *pH*-metric studies of the OBTA complexes with iron (II), cobalt (II), nickel (II), copper (II), zinc (II), cadmium (II), and uranium (VI) ions, which have been carried out in order to establish the composition of these complexes (conductometrically) and also to determine their stability constants in 50% aqueous dioxan medium (*pH*-metrically, employing Bjerrum-Calvin technique).

2-Nitroso-1-naphthol (II), which has the same functional groupings for chelation as (I), is known to form a large number of metal complexes and the data on the stability constants

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of its complexes is reported in 75% aqueous dioxan medium⁸. For a strict comparison of the complexation tendencies of these two ligands, the stability constants of their complexes with the above metal ions have been determined in 50% dioxan—water medium.

EXPERIMENTAL

Oximidobenzotetronic acid (OBTA) was prepared from 4-hydroxycoumarin⁹ and was used as fresh solution; 2-nitroso-1-naphthol (Merck Pro Analyti) was further purified by crystallisation. The solutions of the metal ions were made from either B.D.H. AnalaR or Merck Pro Analyti grade chemicals and were standardised gravimetrically. For *pH*-metric titrations, the metal ion solutions were made in perchloric acid containing 0.6*M* sodium perchlorate (Riedel, L. R.), the strength of the acid being determined titrimetrically¹⁰. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide was prepared from AnalaR grade sodium hydroxide and was standardised against potassium hydrogen phthalate (E. Merck). Dioxan free from water and peroxide was obtained by treating it with sodium wire for 12 hrs and after refluxing the contents for 6 hrs, collecting the fraction distilling at 101-102°.

A Leeds and Northrup drum type conductometer with head-phone was used for the conductance measurements of the solutions; while a Beckman *pH*-meter model H 2 was employed for the measurement of *pH*. The addition of alkali during the *pH* metric titrations was made with the help of an Agla microsyringe fitted with a capillary nozzle.

Conductometric Titrations : 30 ml of *M*/600-metal solution in 40% aqueous ethanol was titrated against *M*/50 OBTA solution in 40% ethanol. Conductance of the solution was measured after each addition of the reagent solution. Plots of conductivity of the solution (after correcting for the increase in volume of the solution) against the moles of OBTA added show distinct inflections in the curves at 1 : 3 metal : ligand ratio for cobalt (II) and iron (II), at 1 : 2 metal : ligand ratio for nickel and copper (II), and at 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 for metal : ligand ratio for uranium (VI), zinc (II) and cadmium (II). A stepwise formation of complexes is indicated only in the case of uranium (VI), zinc (II) and cadmium (II), whereas the lower complexes of cobalt (II), iron (II), copper (II) and nickel (II) do not appear to be sufficiently stable to be detected by the conductometric method.

pH-metric titrations : 10 ml of the metal solution in perchloric acid was pipetted into the titration vessel and 10 ml of reagent solution in dioxan added. Nitrogen gas, pre-saturated with 50% v/v dioxan, was bubbled through the titration vessel and the equilibrium *pH* of the solution was measured after each addition of alkali. The titration was stopped at the appearance of opalescence in the titration solution. The titration was repeated under identical conditions, but omitting the metal and also by omitting the metal and the reagent.

For each metal-ligand system, three sets of titrations containing different amounts of metal and the ligand were carried out.

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9. R. Anschutz, *Ann. Chem.*, 1909, **367**, 169.
10. G. Gran, *Analyst*, 1952, **77**, 661.

From the titration curves, the values of average number of ligands attached per atom of metal ion (\bar{n}) and the free ligand concentration $[L]$, was calculated using the relationships given by Irving and Rossoti¹¹, where the change in volume of the titration solution is negligible and the initial concentration of the free acid can be ignored in comparison with the concentration of the alkali used.

Because the plots of \bar{n} against $\log [L]$ obtained by varying the metal and the ligand concentration were found to be coincident within the experimental error, (Figs. 1. and 2),

FIG. 1

Fig. 1: Bjerrum's formation curves for complexes of OBTA in 50% aqueous dioxan with iron (II) (Δ), nickel (II) (\times), copper (II) (\blacksquare), zinc (II) (\circ), uranium (VI) (\square) and cadmium (II) (\bullet). The curve drawn is the theoretical curve for the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ given in Table I, the points are the experimental values,

the formation of polynuclear complexes was not taken into consideration. Also as the complex formation takes place in the pH range 1.5 to 3.5 for these metal ions, where the metal

11. H. Irving and H. S. Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.

salts are not hydrolyzed, the formation of hydrolyzed complexes was also not considered. The shapes of the formation curves indicated a stepwise complex formation in the case of all metal ion complexes of 2-nitroso-1-naphthol (Fig. 2), whereas in the case of OBTA complexes,

Fig. 2 : Bjerrum's formation curves for complexes of 2-nitroso-1-naphthol in 50% aqueous dioxan with iron (II)(Δ), nickel (II)(\times), Zinc (II)(\circ), Copper (II)(\blacksquare) and uranium (VI)(\square). The curve drawn is the theoretical curves for the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ given in the table, the points are the experimental values.

stepwise complex formation is indicated in the case of nickel (II), cadmium (II), zinc (II) and uranium (VI) complexes. In case of lower complexes of iron (II) and copper (II) with OBTA.

under the experimental conditions, it appears that $\frac{K_1}{K_2} \approx \frac{K_2}{K_3} \approx 0$ and $\frac{K_1}{K_2} \approx 0$ for iron (II) and copper (II) complexes respectively.

The stability constants of the metal-ligand complexes were determined by the two parameter method¹² after writing the relationship between \bar{n} and L for 1 : 2 complex as :

$$\frac{1-\bar{n}}{\bar{n}} [L]K_1 + \frac{2-\bar{n}}{\bar{n}} [L]^2K_1.K_2 = 1$$

the plots of $((1-\bar{n})/\bar{n})[L]$ against $((2-\bar{n})/\bar{n})[L]^2$ giving straight lines having intercepts $1/K_1$ and $1/K_1.K_2$ respectively on the two axes (Figs. 3 and 4). The results obtained are given in Table I.

12. F. J. C. Rossotti and H. S. Rossotti, "The Determination of Stability Constants", McGraw Hill Book Co., Inc., New York, N.Y., 1961.

TABLE I

Stability constants of some metal complexes of oximidobenzotetronic acid and 2-nitroso-naphthol in 50% aqueous dioxan

Temperature = 21°C

pK_a of oximidobenzotetronic acid = 4.25 ± 0.22

pK_a of 2-nitroso-1-naphthol = 8.80 ± 0.02

Metal complex	oximidobenzotetronic acid complex			2-nitroso-1-naphthol complex *		
	log K_1	log K_2	log β_2	log K_1	log K_2	log β_2
Fe(II)	—	—	$12.70 \pm .05^*$	$8.05 \pm .01$	$8.14 \pm .03$	$16.19 \pm .02$
Ni(II)	$4.34 \pm .06$	$4.47 \pm .07$	$8.81 \pm .01$	$7.11 \pm .02$	$6.09 \pm .06$	$13.20 \pm .04$
Cu(II)	—	—	$7.73 \pm .02$	$7.50 \pm .06$	$6.30 \pm .12$	$13.80 \pm .06$
Zn(II)	$3.93 \pm .01$	$3.11 \pm .03$	$7.04 \pm .02$	$5.60 \pm .08$	$5.40 \pm .10$	$10.40 \pm .02$
Cd(II)	$2.16 \pm .03$	$2.68 \pm .05$	$4.84 \pm .02$	—	—	—
UO ₂ (II)	$3.48 \pm .09$	$2.90 \pm .09$	$6.38 \pm .02$	$7.13 \pm .10$	$6.23 \pm .11$	$13.36 \pm .01$

*log β_3

Fig. 3: Plots of $(1-\bar{n})[L]/\bar{n}$ against $(2-\bar{n})[L]^2/\bar{n}$ for OBTA complexes nickel(II) : (Δ); copper(II) : (\blacksquare); zinc(II) : (\circ); uranium(VI) : (\square) and cadmium(II) : (\bullet). X for (Δ) = 10^6 , for (\circ) and (\blacksquare) = 10^6 , for (\square) = 10^7 and for (\bullet) = 5×10^5 . Y for (\blacksquare), (Δ), (\circ) and (\square) = 10^5 , and for (\bullet) = 10^3 .

Oximidobenzotetronic acid (I) which is structurally related to 2-nitroso-1-naphthol (II), is expected to have a lower pK_a value for the dissociation of the proton because of the inductive effect as shown in the formula given earlier. This has been found to be the case experimentally, the pK_a for (I) and (II) being 4.25 and 8.80 respectively in 50% aqueous dioxan medium at 21° in presence of 0.3M sodium perchlorate, determined pH-metrically. The lower basicity of the ligands is expected to give metal complexes having lower stability constants. This is also observed to be the case, the stability constants of OBTA complexes being much lower than the corresponding values for the 2-nitroso-1-naphthol complexes (Table I).

Fig. 4: Plots of $(1-\bar{n})[L]/\bar{n}$ against $(2-\bar{n})[L]^2/\bar{n}$ for 2-nitroso-1-naphthol complexes. Iron (II): (x); nickel (II): (Δ); copper (II): (\blacksquare); Zinc (II): (\circ) and uranium (VI): (\square). X for (x) = 1.25×10^{17} ; for (\blacksquare) = 3×10^{14} ; for (Δ), (\square) = 10^{14} and for (\circ) = 5×10^{10} . Y for (x) = 10^9 ; for (Δ), (\blacksquare) and (\square) = 10^8 and for (\circ) = 10^6 .

From the table it is seen that

- 1) the stability constants for the metal-OBTA complexes do not obey the Irving-William's order¹³, the stability constants for the metal complexes being in the order

and,

- 2) for Nickel(II) complex $\log K_1$ is less than $\log K_2$.

The magnetochemical studies of the solid (isolated) complexes show that the complexes of OBTA with the above metal ions, with the exception of copper (II), are all diamagnetic, indicating thereby the nature of OBTA as a strong field ligand. The deviation in the order of the stability constants¹⁴ of the metal ions may be due to this property of the ligand.

The stability constant of cobalt (II) complexes could not be determined by *pH*-metric titrations because of the ready oxidation of the cobalt(II) complexes to the cobalt (III) complexes.

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